

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-07

BioWAG system
for root-zone water
retention

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Biodegradable soil additive (BioWAG) for root-zone water retention in combination with rainwater harvesting and storage as part of integrated irrigation strategies

INPUTS

Irrigation water (from harvested rainwater, surface water, groundwater, or tap water) and/or rainfall infiltrating into BioWAG-amended soil

OUTPUTS

Water stored and gradually released to plant roots; improved soil moisture stability in the root zone

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 5

CONTEXT & SCALE

Soils with low water-holding capacity (e.g., loamy sand; carbonate rigosols; sandy-loam) and water-efficient irrigation strategies

KEY BENEFITS

Reduced water losses; decreased irrigation frequency; improved water-use efficiency in periods with limited rainfall; potential soil nutrient enrichment during biodegradation

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Effectiveness and the rate and extent of biodegradation depend on soil type, climate conditions, and vegetation used; benefits may gradually decrease over time due to biodegradation of the material

CATEGORY

Biological Water Absorbing Geo-composites (BioWAG)

//02. WHAT IT IS

BioWAG is an innovative, biodegradable soil additive composed of a superabsorbent polymer (SAP), an internal support structure, and a biodegradable nonwoven fabric cover (made from natural materials). It is designed to efficiently store water and gradually release it directly into the root

zone. BioWAG can be optionally enriched with selected beneficial microorganisms, which allows for expanding its functionality and adapting the technology to specific soil conditions, crops, environment and application needs.

Schematic illustration of a BioWAG mat for root-zone water retention (c) UPWR 2025

//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In coarse-textured soils with low water-holding capacity or under high evaporative demands during hot and dry periods,, plants can experience rapid moisture

deficits. By retaining water in the root zone and releasing it gradually, BioWAG supports drought-resilient irrigation strategies and helps stabilize soil moisture availability.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

BioWAG is applied as a soil composite within the root zone to retain infiltrating water. It can be integrated with different irrigation systems (e.g., subsurface distribution; pivot/sprinkler setups) and may be paired with rainwater harvesting and storage.

BioWAG is available in different shapes and sizes adapted to vegetation type and growing conditions. It most commonly takes the form of a 25 × 25cm mat with a thickness of approximately 2-4cm. The material is installed subsurface, allowing roots to grow

through the mat and access stored water. Final dimensions and placement depth should be selected according to plant species, root-zones, irrigation wetting patterns, soil type, and local climate conditions.

The BioWAG mat is applied most often as one unit per plant in a prepared planting hole, concentrating water retention where uptake occurs rather than providing uniform field coverage.

//05. HOW IT WORKS

Due to the composite's absorptive characteristics, infiltrating water is retained within the BioWAG layer. Biodegradation of the BioWAG mat can enrich the soil with nutrients. Stored water is gradually released to plant roots, reducing evaporation and deep percolation losses, and improving irrigation efficiency under drought conditions. The water supply in BioWAG can be replenished repeatedly during subsequent irrigation cycles and/or after rainfall.

Depending on local soil conditions, crop types and management objectives, BioWAG

can be enriched by incorporating selected beneficial microorganisms. These microorganisms can support biological processes in the root zone, such as nutrient cycling, thereby complementing the water retention and release functions of the system. The selection of microorganisms can be adapted to local soil conditions, crop types, and management objectives. A standard BioWAG (25 × 25 × 2cm) can absorb approximately 1.2-1.3 litres of water, depending on field conditions (e.g., water salinity and soil load).

Schematic Illustration of a BioWAG system for root-zone water retention paired with a rainwater harvesting and storage system

Note: Image generated using ChatGPT5.2, OpenAI, with the prompt "Generate a schematic overview using the text of the 'How it Works' factsheet section", 2026

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

Once installed below surface, BioWAG requires minimal maintenance. Routine activities include standard agronomic practices for irrigation which ensure healthy plant development. During establishment, watering may be needed until plants are rooted. Afterwards, BioWAG acts as a moisture buffer, stabilizing water availability, though its water reserve must be replenished periodically.

Regular monitoring of plant condition and root-zone moisture—through visual checks or measurements—helps evaluate performance and adjust irrigation. In the first month, observations should follow stan-

dard cultivation practices; once established, weekly checks are generally sufficient.

BioWAG is biodegradable, and its effectiveness may decline over time. The functional lifetime typically ranges from one to several growing seasons (often 1–3 seasons), depending on material choice and site conditions (soil, climate, biological activity). Reapplication should be based on field observations, as degradation varies with crop, soil, and material type. No dismantling is needed, and once the material loses functionality, it decomposes naturally in the soil.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Nonwoven materials used in BioWAG are biodegradable by design, which over time can reduce mechanical stability and limit functional durability. The rate of degradation and water retention performance depends on environmental conditions such as weather, soil moisture, biological activity, and plant species. As biodegradation progresses, the effectiveness of BioWAG gradually decreases, with a typical duration of action of approximately one to three growing seasons, depending on material choice and site conditions.

Mitigation measures include selecting the BioWAG material according to the intended service life and habitat conditions, as high humidity, elevated temperatures, and strong biological activity can accelerate degradation. Correct installation ensures stable conditions and effective root-zone contact, while regular monitoring of plant health and soil moisture allows irrigation to be adjusted to maintain performance without causing overwatering or waterlogging.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

This solution is particularly useful for both annual and perennial crops farming systems facing seasonal water stress, low water-holding capacity soils or the establishment of young trees. BioWAG is primarily used in agricultural systems, where local (spot) application in the root zone is possible. In large-scale farmland, implementation may be more difficult due to the costs and logistics of installation. Within the

GEORGIA project, BioWAG is implemented together in pilots in [Northern Serbia](#) (Vojvodina region) and in [southwest Poland](#) at the Agricultural and Hydrological Observatory (Wroclaw-Swojec), and, together with rainwater storage, at a pilot site in the [Danube Plain](#) (Brashlen village, Ruse region, Northern Bulgaria).

//09. KEYWORDS

BioWAG; Superabsorbent polymer (SAP); Biodegradable nonwoven fabric; Root-zone water retention; Soil moisture stability;

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. REFERENCES

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//11. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

1. GEORGIA Horizon Europe – BioWAG SAP for circular economy: <https://georgia-horizon.eu/pilots/biowag-sap-for-circular-economy/>
2. D. Marczak, K. Lejcuś, J. Grzybowska-Pietras, W. Biniś, A. Tamma "Circular economy in action: Transforming textile waste into sustainable soil additives – physicochemical properties and biodegradability" *J. Cleaner Prod.* Vol. 480, 2024.
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